

DMP4 nfdi

Data Management Plans
for the German National Research
Data Infrastructure

Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO

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II List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BMBF	German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung)
DALIA	Data Literacy Alliance
DFG	German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)
DMPs	Data Management Plans
DMP facilitators	Those in the NFDI responsible for DMPs or interested in providing discipline-specific DMP knowledge to their communities
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FRL	PUBLISSO – Repository for Life Sciences (Fachrepositorium Lebenswissenschaften)
maDMPs	Machine-actionable Data Management Plans
NFDI	National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur)
OER	Open Educational Resources
RDM	Research Data Management
RDMO	Research Data Manager Organiser
SMPs	Software Management Plans
TtT	Train-the-Trainer

1. Background

1.1. About DMP4NFDI

DMP4NFDI is the basic service in development for data management planning within NFDI [1]. The main objective is to support NFDI consortia in the development and provision of standardised data and software management services. Data Management Plans (DMPs) and Software Management Plans (SMPs) are considered to be an essential component of research data infrastructure, especially in facilitating cooperation among all partners involved in Research Data Management (RDM). While researchers initially and primarily view DMPs as supplements to grant proposals for research funding bodies, their potential extends far beyond this perspective [2].

The basic service aims to provide a standardised framework for RDM throughout the NFDI ecosystem as well as discipline-specific DMP/SMP templates in standardised, machine-readable, and interoperable formats. To support this implementation, DMP4NFDI hosts the open-source tool Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO)¹. Hosting RDMO clients² for the consortia enables cross-consortia collaborative work on catalogs and further service integration. Additionally, the basic service develops an NFDI DMP Template Framework that facilitates the creation of interoperable and standardised templates in RDMO. DMP4NFDI also supports the consortia by offering training, providing training materials as Open Educational Resources (OER), as well as relevant documentation and guidelines.

The development of the basic service DMP4NFDI is funded and supported by the Base4NFDI initiative launched in 2023. Base4NFDI establishes a framework for the development of cross-disciplinary basic services to foster FAIR practices and incorporate the research data management needs of the scientific community within and beyond NFDI into the process. It fosters synergies between the NFDI consortia by supporting the integration, development, and consolidation of the basic services in up to three phases: initialisation, integration, and ramp-up.

1.2. About RDMO

RDMO is a DMP tool initially developed during two DFG-funded projects (2015-2020) and since then further developed as open-source software by its users. It is widely used across Germany at more than 50 research institutions that together form the RDMO community. The tool offers researchers an interview-style interface for data management planning. Users create projects or sub-projects and select a catalog containing several questions on data management. Guided by help texts, examples, and best practices, users create a DMP for their research project. In order to support specific requirements, the RDMO community has developed various catalogs, ranging from general templates suited for funding applications to discipline-specific questionnaires or for generating data policies for collaborative projects. DMPs can be created collaboratively, versioned, and exported in different formats. An API and plugin architecture allows the integration of RDMO with other services.

¹ RDMO: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/>

² RDMO Hosting for Consortia: <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/docs/hosting/>

1.3. DMP-related training and activities in the NFDI consortia

The task areas of the different NFDI consortia include developing services and activities in training, education, support, and outreach to promote and establish effective RDM within their communities. As an important cornerstone of RDM, DMPs are typically included when providing generic RDM knowledge through workshops³, webinars⁴, training materials [3], knowledge platforms⁵, or website articles⁶. This chapter gives insights into DMP-related training and activities in the NFDI consortia.

To better understand the training activities, needs, and challenges of the NFDI consortia regarding DMPs and the use of RDMO, DMP4NFDI carried out an extensive requirement analysis during the initialisation phase. It included exchange with use cases [4], feedback on conducted DMP and RDMO training sessions [5], a survey conducted between March and April 2025, and expert interviews with data stewards involved in the creation of DMPs or DMP templates with RDMO. The survey addressed RDM professionals involved in the creation, use, or training on DMPs, SMPs or RDMO. Of 108 respondents, 58 belonged to at least one consortium, while 50 had no NFDI affiliation. In total, 21 out of 26 NFDI consortia were represented. Of 58 consortium members, 33 answered all survey questions.

Which tasks do you perform in your daily work? Please select all that apply

Based on survey data collected from NFDI consortium members between March and April 2025 (N = 58)

Figure 1. Distribution of daily responsibilities in the NFDI consortia

The survey results show that “Providing RDM support” is the most common general task among consortium members, with 39 mentions (Figure 1). Additionally, respondents affiliated with consortia confirmed that 16 consortia have dedicated RDM teams, and conduct outreach activities for DMPs, SMPs, and/or DMP tools, such as workshops, events, blog or social media posts. The frequency of workshops or webinars on the usage of DMPs or RDMO varies from 1–2 times a year in some consortia to more than six times a year in others, especially if they are included as a topic in general RDM Workshops. The average number of people trained on

³ e.g. NFDI4Chem workshop: <https://www.nfdi4chem.de/a-workshop-for-institutions-fair-research-data-management-basics-for-chemists/>

⁴ e.g. GHGA Webinar: <https://youtu.be/dPySf3gmPCQ?feature=shared>

⁵ e.g. NFDI4Objects Commons Incubator: <https://www.nfdi4objects.net/en/portal/services/commons-inkubator/>

⁶ e.g. Text+ Research Data Management page: <https://text-plus.org/en/themen-dokumentation/forschungsdatenmanagement/>

DMP or RDMO per year can also vary from less than 50 to more than 300, depending on the consortium.

The most common DMP-related task among consortium members is "advising and supporting others in the creation of DMPs" (Figure 2). The results also reveal that the consortia that have not yet created DMP templates or guidelines for their community have an overall interest in developing them.

What are your tasks in relation to data management plans (DMPs)? Please select all that apply

Based on survey data collected from NFDI consortium members between March and April 2025 (N = 53)

Figure 2. Distribution of DMP-related tasks in the NFDI consortia

In terms of RDMO use, 30 consortium respondents reported having already worked with the tool. The majority indicated they use it a few times per year. Respondents highlighted the usefulness of predefined templates tailored to specific funding organizations, such as the DFG, as well as the flexibility to create custom, project-specific templates. Another frequently mentioned strength was the ability to link RDMO to other applications, such as repositories, along with its collaboration features, particularly its capacity to keep DMPs up to date and support workflows through task lists and document previews.

The individual exchange with use cases and representatives from NFDI consortia during the initialisation phase also revealed considerable variation in activities focused on DMPs or the use of DMP tools. While some consortia have been actively using RDMO, such as NFDI4Ing or NFDI4Chem, others have developed their own DMP tool (e.g. DataPLANT's DataPLAN⁷). In some cases, consortia already provide DMP templates or guidelines to their communities. For example, NFDI4Health created three templates⁸ to support health researchers in planning their studies, and NFDI-MatWerk created a guide for its community that outlines best practices for data collection, storage, documentation, sharing, and preservation [6]. However, DMPs or

⁷ DataPLAN: <https://plan.nfdi4plants.org/>

⁸ NFDI4Health Research Data Management Plans: <https://www.nfdi4health.de/en/about-us/task-areas/ta2-standards-for-fair-data/researchdatamanagementplans.html>

DMP tools like RDMO are not yet playing a bigger role in many other consortia, usually due to a variety of challenges, addressed in the next section.

1.4. Challenges in DMP and RDMO support and training in the NFDI consortia

Based on the feedback gathered in our requirements analysis, several recurring challenges emerged that RDM professionals face within NFDI consortia. These include persistent perception gaps from researchers around the added value of DMPs, difficulties in navigating a diverse and sometimes overlapping landscape of funder requirements and DMP templates, and limited resources to sustain DMP training and support efforts. In addition to these consortium-level barriers, we also observed challenges specific to our own train-the-trainer efforts. The following points explore each of these challenges in more detail, summarising the results gathered during the requirement analysis described in section 1.3.

Perception gaps

Consortium members responsible for DMPs often struggle during support and training activities to show the added value of DMPs. There are motivation issues and perception gaps between how DMPs are intended to be used (i.e. as living documents that guide research data management throughout a project) and how researchers currently use and perceive them. Many researchers view DMPs as merely a requirement for funding applications, often completing them only at the proposal stage and neglecting them thereafter. RDM professionals in NFDI report difficulties in motivating their communities to engage with DMPs proactively or to revisit them throughout the lifecycle of a project. A general lack of awareness or understanding of the purpose and benefits of DMPs usually contributes to low engagement. Researchers frequently express confusion about the relevance of DMPs to their specific workflows and struggle to see their long-term value, especially in disciplines where data management practices are less established.

With regard to RDMO, consortium members noted significant barriers stemming from both institutional constraints and user expectations. A key challenge is that some researchers mistakenly assume RDMO is directly linked to institutional IT services, expecting it to function like a helpdesk interface. In consortia where RDMO is not yet centrally supported, consortium members face the added difficulty of promoting a tool that individual researchers could not access independently. While consortium members appreciate RDMO's potential for collaboration and structured planning, they emphasise the importance of clarifying its purpose and functionality early in the training or support process to prevent confusion and foster effective use.

Diversity of templates

Another challenge described by consortium members is navigating the various funder requirements and the large number of templates that have been developed, not only in German-speaking countries, but also internationally and at the European level [2]. When adapting these templates to their community's specific needs, they found that some catalogs are too extensive and not always relevant. Others have gaps or lack clarification on highly relevant topics for the discipline, such as data protection and legal aspects. Consequently, researchers may experience difficulties and therefore be reluctant to complete DMPs based

on such templates. Consortium members highlighted the value of discipline-specific materials, best practices, and templates aligned with funder requirements (e.g., DFG, BMBF, EU Horizon). Knowing which funders require DMPs and having examples that demonstrate reuse or integration into research workflows was cited as particularly useful.

Limited resources

Many NFDI consortia also face a structural challenge in terms of limited resources. In some cases, there is not enough designated personnel to sustain long-term training or support measures on DMPs and RDMO usage. This can affect knowledge retention and limit the development of internal support structures.

Consortium members with diverse backgrounds and learning needs

During our extensive requirement analysis, we identified a wide variation in prior knowledge among potential DMP trainers within the consortia. Participants in future train-the-trainer workshops may enter the training with different backgrounds in RDM, varying experience in RDMO usage, or involvement in DMP template development. This heterogeneity can result in imbalanced learning outcomes if not addressed through differentiated learning opportunities.

New RDMO users often encounter difficulties when first interacting with the tool. These challenges range from navigating the interface to understanding the underlying data model and terminology. Outdated tool documentation and a lack of tailored entry points for different roles (e.g., editors vs. users) can increase cognitive load and deter long-term use. These reflect a need for technical onboarding and operational clarity. There is also a call for guidance on how consortium members can manage their RDMO clients, and how researchers are supposed to access and use them.

These and other challenges are addressed in the training formats and strategy measures described in Section 3.

2. Objectives

The DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer (TtT) concept is part of our mission to provide NFDI-wide, consortia-oriented and reusable trainings for the creation and use of DMPs and SMPs, with RDMO serving as the central tool. It is based on an extensive requirement analysis carried out during the first project phase. Existing training concepts, such as the *FAIRagro concept for training, education and educational resources* [7], the *PID4NFDI Training Concept* [8], and the modular structure and didactic principles tested in the *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management* [9] were used as a model for this first version, which focuses on DMPs and the use of RDMO.

The DMP4NFDI TtT concept aims to enable consortia staff responsible for DMPs to carry out their own training courses and to transfer the knowledge gained to their communities in the long term. To achieve this, the TtT concept

- (1) supports consortia staff responsible for DMPs in developing didactic and communication skills needed to design and deliver effective training sessions on DMPs and RDMO. This includes the ability to explain the purpose, structure, and value of

- DMPs, and guide diverse audiences in the creation of interoperable, machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs);
- (2) supports consortia staff responsible for DMPs in developing a deep understanding of RDMO's technical architecture and underlying data model. This involves hands-on experience with the tool's structure and functionalities to create machine-actionable DMPs;
 - (3) enables consortia staff responsible for DMPs to serve as first-level support within their communities by assisting end users with the use of RDMO and the creation of machine-actionable DMPs. This includes adapting training materials on DMPs and RDMO for specific audiences and providing sustainable, long-term knowledge transfer beyond initial training sessions.

3. Strategy

To achieve these goals, the DMP4NFDI TtT concept addresses those in the consortia responsible for DMPs or interested in providing discipline-specific DMP knowledge to their communities. We will refer to them in this concept as **DMP facilitators**. Existing modular training and education programs for DMPs will be adapted in this first version of the concept to suit this target group and the context in which the training is offered. This will enable future DMP facilitators to adapt well-structured and tested material to the needs of the consortium's community, both during training and during DMP or RDMO support activities.

3.1. Target group

The profiles of possible DMP facilitators within the NFDI consortia are diverse, such as data stewards, software developers, researchers and project coordinators. Consortium members frequently serve as intermediaries between infrastructure and research. Some members possess in-depth knowledge of RDM in their respective disciplines and advise and train researchers in the management of discipline-specific research data. Others yet need to familiarise themselves with the principles of RDM, and therefore DMPs, and how to apply them in their research projects or communities. This train-the-trainer concept addresses both groups. On the one hand, it targets those who are already responsible for data management plans, such as individuals who provide training, consultations, and support to their communities in creating DMPs or developing DMP templates. On the other hand, it is also for those who may have limited experience with DMPs but are interested in offering discipline-specific support and training within their communities.

DMP facilitators may have varying degrees of experience when it comes to using RDMO in its various roles. The tool distinguishes between different users and group types with specific rights⁹. This concept focuses on those using RDMO in the group of "Users" or "Editors". Users can create DMPs and work on them collaboratively, but cannot create DMP templates (catalogs). Editors for a site can access the management interface and edit all catalogs and catalog elements that are then available to users. This concept is aimed at both RDMO beginners and experts in these roles. We define RDMO beginners as those who have little or no prior experience using RDMO to write a DMP or to create DMP templates. Consortium

⁹ RDMO users and groups: <https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration/users.html#roles>

members who create and develop DMP templates are much more likely to have an editor role, while those who advise on DMPs often have a user role.

3.2. Training modules and levels

The DMP4NFDI TtT concept is designed to address the challenges outlined in section 1.4 by offering a training approach that is tailored to the specific roles, responsibilities, and experience of DMP facilitators within NFDI consortia. Its strategy is to support learning at different experience levels and across diverse responsibilities in the DMP process.

The concept provides a modular training approach that supports learners at different levels. The modules are based on the generic learning objectives for the topic of Data Management Plans established in the '*Learning objective matrix on RDM for the target group of students, PhDs and data stewards*' [10]. The matrix proposes generic learning objectives for each RDM topic and tailors them to the various qualification levels of Bachelor, Master, PhD and Data Stewards. Focusing on the target group of "Data Stewards", we have expanded the learning objectives for the topic of DMPs, incorporating new learning objectives that target the use of RDMO and the NFDI DMP Template Framework¹⁰. Finally, we divided the learning objectives into three levels, each building on the previous one:

- **Fundamentals:** provides introductory knowledge about DMPs and RDMO; suitable for those with little or no prior experience
- **Advanced:** offers a more in-depth understanding of DMPs and RDMO, especially for those adapting templates or supporting others
- **Expert:** supports strategic embedding and long-term planning around DMPs and RDMO in the consortium

Each module covers a training topic — i.e., Data Management Plans and RDMO — on all three levels. Each level progressively builds knowledge from foundational DMP concepts to advanced integration in RDMO, thereby ensuring flexibility and adaptability for diverse users. It also includes further aspects about communication and support emphasised during the conducted interviews with data stewards. Modules can also be combined or customised to focus on specific aspects of the research data life cycle.

Additionally, the Train-the-Trainer workshops based on this concept will incorporate the didactic approach and methods outlined in the *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management* [9]. The didactic approach includes the learning process according to Klaus Döring (Figure 3) and how to create a conducive learning atmosphere in a virtual space. Didactic methods will be chosen according to the topics to be covered in the workshops and reviewed with the participants at the end of them.

¹⁰ NFDI DMP Template Framework: https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/shared/DMP4NFDI/NFDI_DMP_Template.md

Figure 3. Learning Model According to Klaus Döring. Reproduced from *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management* [7]

3.2.1. Data Management Plans

Level 1 - Fundamentals

Main objective: DMP facilitators are introduced to the purpose, structure, and benefits of DMPs and maDMPs.

For fundamental content, existing OERs such as the ZB MED training materials [11] are used together with the included materials in the *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management* for the topic of Data Management Plans [9]. At this introductory level, DMP facilitators will learn what a DMP is, gaining a clear understanding of its purpose.

Participants will be able to...

- ... name and explain the general components of a DMP;
- ... explain and discuss the relevance and benefits of DMPs in research projects;
- ... name relevant funding institutions and identify their funding requirements with respect to DMPs;
- ... write a DMP under step-by-step guidance;
- ... recognise the relevance of maDMPs.

DMP facilitators can use this level as a starting point to provide support and training in their communities.

Level 2 - Advanced

Main objective: DMP facilitators with a solid understanding of DMP fundamentals will deepen their expertise to independently write DMPs and effectively support their communities in developing their own.

The advanced level builds on the foundational knowledge established in the first level, guiding participants toward greater independence and deeper insight into the application of DMPs.

Participants will be able to...

- ... discuss and demonstrate the relevance of both DMPs and maDMPs;
- ... compare funder requirements and tailor these requirements to domain-specific needs (e.g., first steps in creating DMP templates);
- ... write DMPs independently;
- ... support researchers writing DMPs (e.g., evaluate the completeness and accuracy of answers).

Level 3 - Expert

Main objective: DMP facilitators will be able to shape community-specific DMP practices through tailored templates, best practices, and targeted training.

The expert level prepares DMP facilitators to take on an active role in shaping data management practices within their consortium and beyond.

At this level, participants will be able to...

- ... independently create DMP templates tailored to the specific needs of their consortium or discipline;
- ... identify and demonstrate good practices for the use of DMPs from a researcher's perspective, helping to connect policy requirements with real-world workflows;
- ... name relevant networks on data management planning to exchange ideas and find support;
- ... design and carry out didactic scenarios on the topic of DMPs, enabling them to train and empower researchers and institutions in a targeted and effective way.

3.2.2. RDMO

Level 1 - Fundamentals

Main objective: DMP facilitators are introduced to the RDMO interface from a general user perspective.

The fundamental level focuses on hands-on usage and familiarisation with the RDMO interface from the perspective of those using RDMO in the group of "Users". It introduces the core functionality and purpose of the tool for creating and managing DMPs.

Participants will be able to...

- ... name and identify RDMO as a suitable tool for creating DMPs;
- ... create and manage projects in RDMO;
- ... use predefined templates to complete DMPs;
- ... complete DMPs navigating through the RDMO interview (question sets);
- ... use RDMO views and export DMPs in common formats;

- ... explain to others the functions of RDMO for creating DMPs;
- ... explain to others how the tool supports the research data lifecycle.

With the completion of this module, DMP facilitators will be confident in using RDMO to draft and manage DMPs. They can use this level as a starting point to provide support and training in their communities.

Level 2 - Advanced

Main objective: DMP facilitators with RDMO editor role are introduced to the management interface of RDMO and the NFDI DMP Template Framework to create catalogs (DMP templates).

The advanced level focuses on hands-on usage and familiarisation with the RDMO interface from an editor's perspective.

Participants will be able to...

- ... explain RDMO's underlying data model, including question sets, attributes, conditions, and option sets;
- ... create new catalogs or modify existing ones, configuring outputs to meet funder or institutional requirements;
- ... use the NFDI DMP Template Framework to create interoperable and standardised catalogs;
- ... operate user roles and permissions.

By the end of this module, DMP facilitators will be able to develop their own catalogs in RDMO, supporting their communities in the effective use of the tool.

Level 3 - Expert

Main objective: DMP facilitators will be able to tailor RDMO to the needs of their community, establishing RDMO as a core service in their consortium.

Building up on the advanced module, the expert level focuses on the strategic application of RDMO as a sustainable, community-aligned service of the NFDI.

Participants will be able to...

- ... independently create catalogs tailored to their community's needs using the NFDI DMP Template Framework;
- ... use the "Tasks" function;
- ... create custom "Views" using their template syntax;
- ... evaluate needs and propose RDMO-based solutions to support data management practices in the consortium;
- ... develop and evaluate strategies for integrating RDMO into their consortium's research workflows and support services;
- ...locate and engage with the RDMO community to exchange ideas and support.

By the end of this module, DMP facilitators will be equipped to position RDMO as a strategic and flexible component of their consortium's RDM landscape.

3.3. Training formats

The format and scope of train-the-trainer courses can be adapted depending on the context and the expertise level of DMP facilitators in the different training topics. The same applies for training courses conducted by the consortia based on this TtT concept.

TtT sessions can vary in length – from short formats (2–4 hours) to more extensive workshops (1–2 half days) – and can be delivered online. It is recommended to plan at least 2 hours for a train-the-trainer course.

Courses may be structured as stand-alone sessions of a topic or as multi-part series that combine different modules, levels, and topics for a more comprehensive learning experience. For example, one train-the-trainer session can combine the advanced DMP knowledge with the fundamentals of RDMO. In-depth, single-topic workshops are particularly recommended for advanced and expert training in RDMO. It is important to note that for an effective combination of modules, the target audience should be rather homogeneous and the trainer should be aware of the knowledge level of the participants in the topics.

Training sessions with participants from various disciplines and expertise levels (e.g. at conferences) can begin with a general introduction to DMPs and the use of RDMO to establish a common foundation. Following this, individual or group exercises with varying levels of difficulty can be offered, allowing participants to engage with the material according to their background and experience. Depending on the planned exercises, we recommend between 12 and 15 participants if there is only one trainer, and up to 25 participants if there are more trainers.

3.4. Feedback

Trainings conducted by DMP4NFDI

Feedback will be collected not only from participants but also from the trainer team to continuously improve the quality of the workshops and the overall concept. Participants' feedback will be gathered during the TtT workshop using methods listed at the end of this section. After the workshop, the DMP4NFDI trainer team will review and evaluate the input received and reflect on the experience from their own perspective, summarising what worked well and identifying areas for improvement. In addition, consortia's feedback will be gathered through incubator projects or meetings of the infra-dmp¹¹ working group to assess how the concept has been applied in community outreach activities. This input will help refine future workshops and ensure they are better aligned with the needs of the NFDI.

Trainings conducted by the consortia based on this TtT concept

Each workshop should include a feedback session to gather opinions on the learning experience. The amount of time scheduled for this (5–15min) will depend on the focus of the workshop and the type of feedback that the trainers want to collect (e.g., verbal vs. written).

¹¹ About the infra-dmp working group: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15001756>

Possible methods for this are listed at the end of this section. Additionally, a pre- or post-workshop evaluation can help to determine whether the learning outcomes have been met.

For example, quizzes or exercises can be used to assess participants' ability to perform the tasks listed in the learning objectives from a previous level. Finally, to assess whether the topics covered have been applied over time, trainers can follow up with participants about six months after the workshop. A short survey could explore, for example, whether DMPs or RDMO are being used, how the training influenced day-to-day work, and what participants would like to see in future sessions. These feedback options help improve future workshops and better align them with the community's needs.

Figure 4. Five-Finger Feedback. Modified from *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management* [7]

Possible feedback methods

One possible method for gathering feedback during a workshop is the Five-Finger Feedback method mentioned in the *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management* [9]. This method has a duration of 10 to 15 minutes and assigns a specific feedback role to each finger (Figure 4). Alternatively, participants can be given 5 to 10 minutes to provide written feedback anonymously through online tools (e.g., Miroboard¹²).

A revised version of the concept will integrate reusable and standardised feedback methods and tools.

¹² Miroboard: <https://miro.com/de/>

4. Measures

4.1. Training delivery

Within the framework of incubator projects¹³, DMP4NFDI will offer train-the-trainer workshops for the NFDI consortia. Additionally, they will adapt this concept to provide workshops at conferences.

4.1.1. Cooperation with NFDI Consortia via incubator projects

Time plan: A first train-the-trainer session will be conducted at the end of the initialisation phase with pilot consortia (June 2025). Other training sessions will be conducted during the integration phase (July 2025–June 2027) via incubator projects. An incubator project is a short-term engagement (3–6 months) with a clearly defined goal, in this case: support with training activities and community outreach.

Target Group: DMP facilitators in the NFDI

Expertise level: The knowledge levels required for the successful completion of incubator projects will depend on the project and the needs of the consortium.

Format: Online

Spoken language: English or German, based on the requirement or the audience

Material language: English

Duration: The training session will last between one and three hours, depending on the project, the modules and levels chosen, and the needs of the consortium.

4.1.2. Workshops at conferences

Time plan: One to two workshops per year at conferences based on this concept during the integration phase.

Target group: DMP facilitators

Target size: 15–25, depending on the number of trainers.

Expertise level: depends on the module and level chosen, if the group is homogeneous. In case of mixed groups, it is recommended to start with the first level.

Format: In-person or Online, depending on the event.

Spoken language: English or German, depending on the event.

¹³ DMP4NFDI incubator projects: <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/incubator/>

Material language: English

Duration: The workshops will last between one and two hours, depending on the organiser's specifications.

4.2. Open Educational Resources

DMP4NFDI will provide training materials under open license in three forms: referring to existing training materials, providing training materials used in DMP4NFDI workshops, and creating self-learning materials.

4.2.1. Provision of training materials

DMP4NFDI will provide an overview of existing open educational resources (OER) on DMP fundamentals in cooperation with RDMTraining4NFDI that can be used by NFDI consortia when providing level 1 DMP training to their communities.

Additionally, the training materials used during DMP4NFDI workshops will be made available to participants as OER after the workshops. The OER will be prepared in such a way that it can easily be reused by NFDI to follow up on the training content or to adapt the training material to specific disciplines.

4.2.2. Creation of self-learning materials for RDMO

In collaboration with the RDMO community, DMP4NFDI will provide materials that DMP facilitators can use to learn how to use RDMO independently. These materials will be available on the RDMO website so that they can be used as part of training events or to create new training materials. The materials will also be linked on the DMP4NFDI website.

4.2.3. Publication

The OER will be published on PUBLISSO – Repository for Life Sciences (FRL)¹⁴ and added to the DMP4NFDI community on Zenodo. They will also be made discoverable in other portals for open educational resources, such as DALIA (Data Literacy Alliance)¹⁵. In addition, the materials will be linked on the DMP4NFDI website so that they can be found via this central point of contact for NFDI.

¹⁴ PUBLISSO – Repository for Life Sciences (FRL):
<https://www.publisso.de/en/publishing/repositories/repository-for-life-sciences>

¹⁵ DALIA: <https://dalia.education/en>

5. Outlook for the integration phase

The TtT concept will be continuously expanded and evaluated through incubator projects and ongoing exchange with NFDI during the integration phase. The goal is to ensure that the training topics, formats, and material remain sustainable, reusable, and responsive to the evolving needs of the consortia.

A key focus will be the integration of SMPs as a new module and the evaluation of training topics provided in this concept. As part of this, DMP4NFDI will examine how a network of DMP trainers in the consortia could be further encouraged, e.g., together with RDMTraining4NFDI. Such a network would promote the exchange of best practices and up-to-date materials, and foster cooperation within and beyond the NFDI.

Training formats provided in this concept will also be reviewed to determine if new approaches can be developed, such as self-study modules for DMPs. These would support flexible integration into the consortia's training structures. Alternatively, targeted exchange activities among experts may be more effective and will be explored accordingly.

To enable comparable results in DMP training over time, a revised version of the concept will evaluate and incorporate standardized feedback methods. These will support consistent evaluation across workshops and consortia, making it easier to identify trends and training needs related to DMPs and RDMO. They will also strengthen evidence-based improvements and facilitate more transparent reporting on training impact.

Lastly, the TtT concept will include exemplary module combinations within the materials for two to three common training scenarios. It will also assess the feasibility of converting teaching scripts and additional learning materials to LiaScript, enabling their publication as OER. This would ensure easy reuse, adaptation, and long-term accessibility of core training content.

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